

Source: Daraie M, [Heravi MM](#), Kazemi SS. Pd@GO/Fe₃O₄/PAA/DCA: a novel magnetic heterogeneous catalyst for promoting the Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction. J Coord Chem. 2019;72(13):2279-93. DOI: [10.1080/00958972.2019.1640360](https://doi.org/10.1080/00958972.2019.1640360)

Pd@GO/Fe₃O₄/PAA/DCA: a novel magnetic heterogeneous catalyst for promoting the Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction

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Abstract

A hybrid system involving graphene oxide (GO), magnetic oxide (Fe₃O₄), acrylamide and dicyandiamide was prepared via amine functionalization of GO/Fe₃O₄ by means of covalent bonding with acrylamide and subsequent reaction with dicyandiamide to provide a multinitrogen containing polymer on the surface of GO. This hybrid system was utilized as a heterogeneous catalyst support for immobilizing Pd nanoparticles to provide the hybrid, Pd@GO/Fe₃O₄/PAA/DCA. This nano-Pd composite was characterized using Fourier transform infrared, transmission electron microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, vibrating sample magnetometer, thermogravimetric analysis, X-ray diffraction, and ICP techniques and used for promoting Sonogashira cross-coupling under mild reaction conditions. This heterogeneous and magnetic catalyst was easily separated by external magnet and was reused in a model reaction, efficiently up to six times with slight loss of catalytic activity and Pd leaching, showing the suitability of GO/Fe₃O₄/PAA/DCA for embedding Pd nanoparticles. To check the effect of the number of surface nitrogens of the polymeric chain on the catalytic performance, the activity of the catalyst was compared with Pd@GO/Fe₃O₄/PAA; increased number of the surface nitrogens on the chain polymer leads to higher loading of Pd and lower the Pd leaching.

Keywords: GO, Fe₃O₄, acrylamide, dicyandiamide, Pd nanoparticles, copper and ligand-free, Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction